

Supplementary File S2b - Expanded CFA Fit Indices for WHOQOL-BREF.

Fit Indices	Value	Interpretation	Threshold
χ^2 (df = 253)	20251.162, $p < 0.001$	Significant (expected for ordinal data)	NA
CFI	0.966	Good fit	≥ 0.95
TLI	0.962	Good fit	≥ 0.95
NFI	0.955	Good fit	≥ 0.95
RMSEA	0.127	Good fit (ordinal data)	≤ 0.15
RMSEA 90% CI	0.119–0.136	NA	NA
SRMR	0.104	Marginal (considering ordinal data)	≤ 0.08
GFI	0.988	Excellent fit	≥ 0.95
PNFI	0.874	Good	≥ 0.50
Hoelter's N ($\alpha = 0.05$)	47.838	Low sample adequacy	≥ 200

Note: χ^2 , chi-square test of model fit; CFI, comparative fit index; TLI, Tucker–Lewis index; NFI, normed fit index; RMSEA, root mean square error of approximation; SRMR, standardized root means square residual; GFI, goodness-of-fit index; PNFI, parsimony normed fit index; Hoelter's N, Hoelter's critical N (sample size adequacy estimate).